

Investigations on polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in waste oil at Mathura-Agra, National Highway No. 2

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Manuscript received 19 November 2007, accepted 21 January 2008

Abstract : Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) are released into the environment from anthropogenic sources, such as combustion of refused burning, industrial process, electrical equipment. The concentration of PAHs in roadside oil-sludge was measured at outside of Mathura-Refinery, Delhi-Agra, National Highway No. 2. The samples were extracted with *n*-hexane by ultrasonic agitation and aromatic fraction analysis by GC. Total mean concentration of PAHs was found to be 11.34 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ and ranged from 4.43–22.53 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$. Fluoranthene, chrysene, benzo (b) fluoranthene were found to be the most abundant PAHs at this location.

Keywords : Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs), fluoranthene, chrysene.

Introduction

Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) are made up of carbon, hydrogen and at least two fused benzene rings. They are formed during incomplete-combustion of organic materials and geochemical formation of fossil fuels and are the products of thermal decomposition. Sources of PAHs include refineries, power plants, automobiles. It is well established that some PAHs have carcinogenic, mutagenic and immunotoxic effects on animals and can occur in low concentration in many parts of the environment¹. The reports have been received from Los Angles, USA²; Ontario, Canada³; Massachusetts, USA⁴; Anthens, Greece⁵; Lahore, Pakistan⁶ and even in Mumbai, India⁷. Due to their mutagenic and carcinogenic potential, the atmospheric concentration of PAHs in many geographical locations of the world have been measured and reported^{8–22}. In many circumstances, the environmental occurrence of PAHs has been associated with adverse effects on public health. It is believed that there is no 'Threshold' or 'Safe' level for the mutagenic compounds, hence exposure to these PAHs at any level provide the risk of toxic effects.

The concentration determined for individual PAH will help Planners, Scientists and Administrators to draw strategies to reduce PAH exposure to the people living in this area. The aim of this study is to investigate the occurrence of PAHs at roadside oil-sludge outside of Mathura Refinery.

Materials and methods :

Regional site description : Agra, the City of Taj (27° 10'N, 78°02'E) is located in the north central part of India having 1,391,000 of total population⁸. It is bounded by the arid Thar desert of Rajasthan on two-third part of its periphery. The climate during summer is hot and dry with temperature ranging from 32°C to 48°C. In winter, the temperature ranges from 10.5°C to 30.5°C. The downward wind is south-southeast i.e. SSE 29% and north-east i.e. NE 6% in summer and it is west-northwest i.e. WNW 9.4% and north-northwest i.e. NNW 11.8% in winter. The atmospheric pollution load is high because of the downward wind, pollutants may be transported to the different areas mainly from an oil refinery situated in Mathura (50 km from the Centre of Agra City). Outside of Mathura Refinery oil-sludge at roadside sampling site.

Sample collection : The surface oil-sludge samples were collected from roadside at outside of Mathura-Refinery, Delhi-Agra National Highway No. 2. Ten samples were collected, dried at room temperature in a dark room and then sieved through 20-mesh sieve and stored in polybags at 4°C.

Extraction and analysis : 1.0 g of oily-sludge sample were extracted for 45 min with *n*-hexane (2.0–10.0 ml) in an ultrasonic bath extractor.

Chemicals : All solvents were GC-pure quality and were purchased from Supelco and Sigma-Aldrich Inc. (Germany). A working stock solution was prepared from PAHs compound mix standard containing 10 μg of each

in 1 ml of *n*-heptane.

Instrumentation : Analysis of PAHs sample was done by GC (Hewlett-Packard) equipped with μ FID detector, split/splitless injection system and capillary columns, the extract is ready for analysis by GC method 8100. Nitrogen, 42 ml min⁻¹ used as a carrier gas. Gas chromatography system are characterized in Table 1.

Table 1

Gas chromatograph	Hewlett-Packard-5890 Series-II
Detector	μ FID, 320°C, N ₂ Make up, 60 ml min ⁻¹
Column	Quartzitic capillary column HP-5
Gas carrier	Nitrogen, 42 ml min ⁻¹
Injector temperature	250°C
Detector temperature	300°C
Oven	First ramp - 100 (hold 1 min) to 190°C at 30°C min ⁻¹ Second ramp - 190°C to 280°C (hold 1 min) at 6°C min

Results and discussion

The statistical data for individual PAH and total PAHs for outside of Mathura-Refinery oil-sludge are tabulated in Table 2. The PAHs concentrations ranged from 4.43–22.53 μ g g⁻¹. The mean concentrations of total PAHs for the entire samples collected was 11.34 μ g g⁻¹.

Table 2. Concentrations of PAHs in oil-sludge

PAHs	Mean	Range
Naphthalene	0.98	0.27–2.07
Acenaphthylene	0.59	0.08–1.60
Phenanthrene	0.44	0.14–1.18
Anthracene	0.91	0.10–1.93
Fluoranthene	1.13	0.36–2.97
Pyrene	1.90	1.11–2.71
Chrysene	3.50	1.91–5.81
Benzo (b) fluoranthene	1.22	0.31–2.61
Benzo (k) fluoranthene	0.26	0.06–0.69
Benzo (a) pyrene	0.41	0.09–0.96
Total PAHs	11.34	4.43–22.53

The concentrations for all the individual ten PAHs are shown in Fig. 1, i.e. naphthalene (0.98 μ g g⁻¹), acenaphthylene (0.59 μ g g⁻¹), phenanthrene (0.44 μ g g⁻¹), anthracene (0.91 μ g g⁻¹), fluoranthene (1.13 μ g g⁻¹), pyrene (1.90 μ g g⁻¹), chrysene (3.50 μ g g⁻¹), benzo (b) fluoranthene (1.22 μ g g⁻¹), benzo (k) fluoranthene (0.26 μ g g⁻¹), benzo (a) pyrene (0.41 μ g g⁻¹).

Fig. 1. Individual concentrations of PAHs in μ g g⁻¹.

From Fig. 2, it is clear that 2 and 3 ring compounds (naphthalene, acenaphthylene, phenanthrene, anthracene) found in low concentration than 4, 5 ring compounds (fluoranthene, pyrene, benzo (b) fluoranthene, chrysene, benzo (k) fluoranthene, benzo (a) pyrene).

Fig. 2. Classification of different PAHs with their concentrations in μ g g⁻¹ based on the number of rings of benzene.

The reason behind this is 2 and 3 ring compounds are of lighter molecular weight and therefore they are highly volatile in nature, while the compounds of 4, 5 rings are not volatile due to their high molecular weight. 4, 5 ring compounds are carcinogenic and mutagenic.

Conclusion :

This investigation was conducted adjacent to the outside of refinery, major source of PAHs in oil-sludge. The total mean concentration of PAHs at outside of Mathura Refinery oil sludge was $11.34 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$.

A set of ten PAHs was found in oil-sludge including fluoranthene, pyrene, chrysene, benzo (b) fluoranthene (HMW, PAHs) having the mean concentrations $1.13 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, $1.90 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, $3.50 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, $1.22 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ respectively.

This study indicated that PAHs 4–5 rings with higher molecular weight found deposited in higher proportions to the outside of refinery. This preliminary investigation needs to be further explored considering many more parameters and extending the locations representing other activities. It is also possible that the chemistry of PAHs in a tropical environment, where the ambient temperature and relative humidity are higher coupled with abundant sunshine, may differ from that of temperate regions.

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